

PSYCHOLOGY OF THINKING AND THE PSYCHOLOGICAL ESSENCE OF CRITICAL THINKING

*F. Pulatova*¹

Abstract:

This article describes the following stages of the thinking process, objects, features and relationships, forms and laws of thinking, logic, and its mechanisms of action.

Key words: thinking, critical, problem, mind, mental

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/c48raw60>

Thinking, unlike other processes, is carried out according to a certain logic.

Thinking is a mental process of generalized and indirect reflection of stable regular features and relationships of reality, which is carried out for solving cognitive problems, systematic orientation in certain situations. Mental activity is a system of mental actions, operations to solve a specific problem.

According to associationism, thinking itself is not a special process and comes down to a simple combination of memory images (node, similarity, contrast associations). Representatives of the Würzburg school considered thinking as a separate type of mental processes and separated it from the emotional basis and speech. According to psychology, thinking happens in a closed area of the mind. As a result, thinking is reduced to the movement of thoughts in the closed structures of the mind. Materialistic psychology approached thinking as a process that is formed in the social conditions of life and takes the character of internal "mental" actions.

Thinking is the highest level of human knowledge. It makes it possible to obtain knowledge about such objects, properties and relations of the real world that cannot be directly perceived on a sensory level. Forms and laws of thinking are studied by logic, and its mechanisms of action are studied by psychology and neurophysiology. Cybernetics analyzes thinking in relation to the tasks of modeling certain mental functions.

Thinking is active and problematic. It focuses on solving problems. The following stages of the thinking process are distinguished:

Awareness of the problem situation - there is awareness that there is information about the deficit. You should not think that this is the beginning of thinking, because understanding the problem situation already includes the initial thought process.

Knowing the developing solution as a hypothesis involves searching for solutions.

Hypothesis testing stage - the mind carefully weighs the pros and cons of its hypotheses and tests them comprehensively.

Solving a problem is getting an answer to a question or solving a problem. The decision is confirmed in the court decision on this matter.

Mental operations. Thought patterns.

1. Analysis - breaking down the whole into parts or properties (shape, color, etc.).
2. Synthesis - mental combination of parts or properties into a whole

¹ *Pulatova Farida Azamovna, Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages*

International Conference

ADVANCED METHODS OF ENSURING QUALITY OF EDUCATION: PROBLEMS AND OPPORTUNITIES

3. Comparison - comparing things and events, finding similarities and differences
4. Generalization - a mental association of things and events according to common important signs
5. Abstraction - selection of some features and distraction from others.
6. Concretization is the opposite process to abstraction. We use specific events.

These operations are not different adjacent and independent variants of mental actions, but there is a coordination relationship between them, because they are specific, specific forms of the main, general mental operation of mediation. In addition, the arbitrary arrangement of thinking creates the possibility of reversal of operations: separation and connection (analysis and synthesis), establishing similarities and identifying differences (or comparison).

References:

- [1]. Donald Laser, "Invention, Critical Thinking and Political Rectoration of Analysis"
- [2]. American Philosophical Association, *Consensus Statement of Critical Thinking Act*, 1990
- [3]. John C. Bean, *Thought Engagement: Professor's Guide to Active Learning in Writing, Critical Thinking and Testing*, 2nd, Wiley, 2011 || *Academic research journal IF-7.4 January 2023 Volume 1 Issue 7* <https://academicsresearch.com/index.php/IARJ/index> 72
- [4]. Kristin R. Woolever, *About Writing: Rhetoric for Good Writers*, Wadsworth, 1991 www.skillsyouneed.com
- [5]. Pulatova F. A. *Psychology of critical thinking for students* // *International Academic Research Journal Impact Factor*. – 2023. – Т. 7. – С. 67-73.
- [6]. Рахимова, З. С. (2023). *Functional-semantic analysis of microsystems of kinship terms in Uzbek and English languages*. *Международный журнал искусство слова*, 6(5).